

AN INVESTIGATION OF THE INDIAN BANKING SECTOR: THE INFLUENCE OF ONLINE TRAINING AND JOB SATISFACTION ON ENHANCING EMPLOYEE RETENTION

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Abstract

Human resources play a pivotal role in the effective and proper functioning of any organization; thus, a firm must focus not only on recruiting a highly qualified and experienced workforce but at the same time must give due consideration to retaining the employee for a long span of time. In order to determine and evaluate the relationship between employee training and employee retention, the current investigation evaluates the research findings and results. Training is an essential tool for any organization, specifically when it comes to updating new skills and knowledge of employees in this dynamic environment. Questionnaires, both online and offline, are being circulated for conducting this research, and quantitative research methods in the form of regression analysis and correlation are used to test the hypothesis. The current research paper focuses on the effect of online training and job satisfaction on employee retention in India's banking sector. The research finding implies a significant relationship between job satisfaction, training programs, and employee retention. Thus, effective online training must be provided to the employee in order to help them boost their already existing knowledge, leading to an increase in their self-satisfaction and reducing their turnover ratio.

Keywords: *Employee Retention, Job Satisfaction, Online Training, Human Resource Management.*

INTRODUCTION

Retaining a skilled and experienced workforce has become a critical challenge and an important component of organizational success in the rapidly evolving and competitive Indian banking sector. Maintaining a knowledgeable and qualified workforce is particularly important as banking institutions regulate the constantly shifting market demands and the quickening pace of advancements in technology. Effective training programs and satisfaction with work are the main components that compel the workforce to stay in the organization for a long. The top manager must formulate HR policies and strategies to enhance retention **(Elsafty & Oraby, 2022; Mózo, 2017)**. The main aim of employee retention is to avoid losing a competent workforce, which will affect the organization's productivity **(Bansal et al., 2014; Soenanta et al., 2020)**. Employee retention is the major focus of today's organization **(Oladapo, 2014)**.

Online training is a major source of improving and updating employees' skills since it is a convenient and economical method. Organizations can bridge the skill gap and maintain continuous growth through the learning of employees by organizing various training programs and initiatives both inside as well as outside the premises. Up to date, the training program will enable the employees to resolve their problems and will provide them with possible solutions for solving them, leading to overall satisfaction with their current job by boosting their confidence with regard to their work and ultimately leading to employee retention. The Organizing training program for employees during the job improves their skills **(Hanaysha & Tahir, 2016)**. Training employees is a learning experience that brings positive change in the behavior of employees in order to enhance productivity and creativity in employees **(Bhakuni, 2023; Gómez-Redondo et al., 2024)**. Training is the process of making others help and understand various skills, processes, and techniques to reskill and upskill in an organization **(Wadhwa & Sahay, 2024)**. Training is the function of developing worker skills and knowledge, thereby leading to an increase in productivity, job satisfaction, and employee retention **(Beynon et al., 2015; Elsafty & Oraby, 2022)**.

Job satisfaction is another main determinant that induces people to remain in the organization for a long period. It mainly comprises the overall gratification of an employee with the work environment, work culture, their work role, etc. Reduced turnover, higher level of loyalty, commitment toward the employer and with their work, and higher productivity are the outcomes of a high level of job satisfaction among the employees. The higher the level of job satisfaction, the higher the retention rate, leading to a good image of the organization. Understanding job satisfaction and job performance of employees in most of the developed countries is vital for the success of any organization **(Nguyen, 2021)**. **(Ladeira et al., 2012; Rezende Barbosa et al., 2016; Steil et al., 2020)** Job satisfaction in the public sector differs from the private sector; the private sector encourages competition, efficiency, and profit **(Ladeira et al., 2012; Rezende Barbosa et al., 2016; Steil et al., 2020)**. Job satisfaction is a positive feeling toward work, while job dissatisfaction is a negative attitude toward work **(Robbins, 1964; Soenanta et al., 2020)**. Generally, researchers accept that training increases job satisfaction among employees and, thereby, the length of employment **(Chiang & (Shawn) Jang, 2008; Prasad, 2021)**. Job satisfaction is directly related to individual behavior in the workplace **(Biaison, n.d.; Davies et al., 1985)**.

Even though job satisfaction and training have been thoroughly investigated in general settings of organizations, To our knowledge fewer considerations have been dedicated to how these variables specifically impact staff retention in banking organizations in India leading to originality of our

research work . In the long run, addressing these gaps might result in more effective techniques for boosting employee engagement and minimizing turnover by providing a greater awareness of how job satisfaction and online training work together to influence the retention of workers in the Indian banking industry. Thus, in order to address this gap, the current study answer the following question:

- 1. Do Online training leads to employee retention for long span of time in Indian banking sector?**
- 2. Do Job Satisfaction has significant influence in retaining employee in banking sector?**

By assessing the interrelationship among these three determinants, we aim to identify how this i.e. online training and job satisfaction impacts employee retention in the Indian banking organization. This objective also helps the banking sector formulate strategies and policies that reduce the turnover rate in the organization and lead to increases in their commitment to the workplace.

This paper is divided as follows: **Section 2** consists of a literature review. **Section 3** introduces the research variable and hypothesis formulated **Section 4** constitute the model of the study, **Section 5** includes the Research methodology **Sections 6 and 7** present the finding and implications of the study **Section 8 and 9** shows Limitation, the conclusion &future research.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Training and development influence organizational identification and employer branding, and the association between training and development and employer branding is mediated by organizational identification (**Bharadwaj, 2023**). Training and development significant influence on employee retention and commitment in the banking sector in India, **Aleem, M., & Bowra, Z. A. (2020)**. The findings demonstrate that training and rewards had significant effects on job satisfaction, and that in turn have a positive impact on employee retention. Training, by its own, however, has little direct effect on retention, demonstrating that job satisfaction mediates the relationship(**Alrazehi et al., 2021**).

Training and development and job satisfaction directly influence employee retention, but job performance does not significantly affect employee retention, and there is no association between effective communication, job performance, and employee retention, according to (**Elsafty & Oraby, 2022**). Training and development, job satisfaction, and job performance positively impact young employee retention in Vietnamese organizations(**Nguyen, 2021**). Retention of employees is directly impacted by training and development, and supervisor support. At the same time, the working environment acts as a moderating variable between training and development, supervisor support, and employee retention (**Palwasha et al., 2018**). Different modes of training, whether online or offline mode, have a different impact on employee performance; the effectiveness of different modes depends on various factors like the ability of the trainer, the level of trainees, the content of the training, the applicability of training to work, etc (**Sahay, 2024**) The more training and development of banking employees there is, the higher the chances of employees being retained (**Abba, 2018**). Satisfaction with salary reveals a positive association with the retention of public and private employees in IT institutions (**Steil et al., 2020**). Compensation, training, and development proactively influence job satisfaction, but organizational culture does not. Compensation also stimulates employee retention, while training and development and organizational culture do not.

Job satisfaction enhances employee retention, and training and development improve retention indirectly through job satisfaction (**Murtiningsih, 2020**). Training and development programs have a desirable effect on employee retention, engagement, and overall organizational performance. This is congruent with Maslow's model, which posits that meeting employees' needs enhances their performance and satisfaction (**Bhakuni, 2023**). Employee retention is directly impacted by job satisfaction and organizational commitment (**Soenanta et al., 2020**). Transfer performance is influenced by three main factors: learning motivation, training content, and learning environment (**Titan et.al., 2014**). Training is directly related to training satisfaction and job satisfaction, and job satisfaction is ultimately related to the intention to stay in the hotel industry, Thus, organizations should focus more and more on providing training to workers (**Chiang & Hsieh, 2012**). There is a positive correlation between job satisfaction and employee retention (**Biason, n.d.**). Employee retention depends mainly on various factors like training and development, growth opportunities for the employees, employee benefits, employee self-attainment, etc. (**Akther et al., 2020**). Employee rewards affect employee retention, but do not affect job satisfaction (**Terera & Ngirande, 2014**).

Research variables & Hypotheses Formulated:

Online Training:

Online training is a digital training program offered to employees by the employer in order to enhance their skills in order to enhance their work performance. In the ever-changing world, online training has become a reputable and the most flexible method of increasing knowledge as well as shaping the capabilities of an individual, it is a systematic application of web-based tools to provide knowledge to individuals (**Mcgraw-2001, Wittayakom et al., 2024**)

Past researchers have studied in their work that Training and development, job satisfaction, and job performance positively impact young employee retention in Vietnamese organizations (**Nguyen, 2021**). Retention of employees is directly impacted by training and development (**Palwasha et al., 2018**). The more training and development of banking employees there is, the higher the chances of employees being retained (**Abba, 2018**). Thus, on the basis of this following hypothesis is formulated:

H₁: Online training has a positive and significant effect on employee retention.

Job satisfaction: According to Robbins (2006), job satisfaction refers to an individual's overall attitude about his work and the variance between the amount of compensation he receives and what he feels should be accepted. Employee behavior in the workplace can be driven by job satisfaction, which may result in a high intention to leave. In accordance with the study, there is a relationship between employee job satisfaction and retention; the higher the sense of job satisfaction, the higher the perception of retention (Murtiningsih, 2020). Based on the study, employee retention in both public and commercial IT enterprises is correlated with job satisfaction and salary (Steil et al., 2022). As job satisfaction is the main driver that keeps employees with a company, it is vital. However, job satisfaction is essential for peak performance since it motivates and inspires workers to accomplish goals at work.

H₂: Job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on employee retention.

Model of the Study:

This is the proposed model of the study: Online Training and Job Satisfaction is the independent variable, while Employee Retention is the Dependent variable of the study. This model depicts the impact of Both Independent variables on the Dependent variable

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework of the Study

Source: Author's Computation

Source: Author's Computation from past literature

Objectives:

The following are the objectives of the study:

- 1) To examine the Influence of Online Training on Employee Retention in the Indian banking Sector
- 2) To analyze the impact of Job Satisfaction on Employee Retention in the Indian banking Sector

METHODOLOGY

The current research paper is empirical in nature. A descriptive research design is used to carry out this research. Multiple regression analysis and correlational analysis have been used to analyze the relationship between independent and dependent variables. G Power software is used to calculate the sample size, which consists of 159 respondents. Employees of both Private as well as public banks were used for the collection of data. Purposive sampling was used as a sampling technique targeting only the employees of the bank. The questionnaire was adapted from the past literature. There are three variables in the questionnaire. Each variable consists of four items and four demographic questions, comprising a total of 16 questions in a questionnaire.

ANALYSIS OF THE FINDINGS

Demographic profile:

Table 1: Gender

Gender		Frequency	Percent
	Female	61	38.4
	Male	98	61.6
	Total	159	100.0

Source: Author's Computation

Table 1 presents the total number of males and females. Females comprise 38.4% of the total sample size, and the remaining 61.6 % consists of males.

Table 2: Age

Age		Frequency	Percent
	Below 30	88	55.3
	30 – 40 Years	52	32.7
	41- 50	12	7.5
	Above 50	7	4.4
	Total	159	100.0

Source: Author's Computation

The highest number of respondents is in the age group below 30, i.e., 55.3 % of the total sample size, while the least number of people is in the age group above 50, i.e., 4.4 %, as shown in Table 2

Table 3: Job position

Levels	Frequency	Percent
Junior level	61	38.4
Middle level	80	50.3
Top-level	18	11.3
Total	159	100.0

Source: Author's Computation

In Table 3, the percentage of junior-level employees is 38.4 %, middle-level employees is 50.6 % and top-level employees are 11.3 %.

Table 4: Employed in which bank

Bank	Frequency	Percent
Public bank	70	44.0
Private Bank	89	56.0
Total	159	100.0

Source: Author's Computation

Table 4 represents the percentage of people employed in private and public banks of the total sample size. The highest percentage of private bank employees is 56%, and the remaining 44% are public bank employees.

Table 5: Descriptive statistics

	N	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard deviation	variance	Skewness	kurtosis		
OT	159	13.00	3.25	16.25	7.7610	3.34682	11.201	.928	.192	.339	.383
JS	159	13.00	3.25	16.25	8.5692	3.26056	10.631	.692	.192	.047	.383
ER	159	13.00	3.25	16.25	8.3333	3.40893	11.621	.570	.192	-.334	.383
Valid N (listwise)	159										

Source: Author’s Computation

Table 5 above depicts the descriptive interpretation of variables. In this research, we collected 159 respondents. The difference between the maximum and minimum statistics of online training, job satisfaction, and employee retention is 13.00. The minimum value of all three variables is 3.25, while the maximum value is 16.25. The mean of online training is 7.76, while those of job satisfaction and employee retention are 8.56 and 8.33. Standard deviation measures the deviation among data sets. OT has a 3.36 standard deviation; JS has 3.26, and ER has 3.4, which highlights that ER has the highest standard deviation, suggesting greater variability, while JS has the lowest standard deviation, suggesting the lowest variability. Dispersion can be measured by variance, which is proportional to the product of the mean variance. Likewise, the standard deviation, the variance of ER, is the most significant. The asymmetry of the data distributions is determined through skewness. A positive skewness result indicates a right-skewed in the data distribution. OT is the most right-skewed, with the largest positive skewness, a value of 0.928, followed by JS, i.e., 0.692, and ER, i.e., 0.557. In contrast to a normal distribution, the OT distribution is slightly more peaked with a 0.33 value and has heavier tails due to its slightly positive kurtosis. In light of its almost-normal distribution and absence of excessive peakiness or flatness, JS's kurtosis is close to 0, i.e., 0.47. The overall distribution of ER is flatter, with lighter tails and fewer extreme values, as indicated by kurtosis Shown by its negative value of -.33.

Table 6: Reliability Result

Cronbach alpha value:	0.954
Number of items:	12

Source: Author’s Computation

Reliability is the measure of the internal consistency of the constructs in the study. A construct is reliable if the alpha value is greater than 0.7. Table 6 highlights that Cronbach’s alpha value was 0.954, close to 1, which depicts higher internal consistency. This means a questionnaire is reliable for the collection of data.

Table 7: Correlation analysis result

	OT	JS	ER
OT	1		
JS	.751**	1	
ER	.741**	.858**	1

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). **

Source: Author’s Computation

The correlation coefficient (r) value between online training and employee retention is 0.741, which shows a positive association between both variables. The p-value is < 0.01, which means the relation is statistically significant. So, we can say that an increase in online training also increases the employee retention rate. Hence, H1 is supported the correlation coefficient (r) value between Job satisfaction and employee retention is 0.858, which shows a high positive association between both variables. The p-value is <0.01, which means that an increase in the level of job satisfaction increases the employee retention rate. Hence, H2 is supported

Table 8: Regression analysis result

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.871 ^a	.758	.755	1.68341

Predictors: (Constant), JS, OT_a
 Source: Author’s Computation

ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	1384.589	2	692.294	244.293	.000 ^b
	Residual	442.084	156	2.834		
	Total	1826.673	158			
a. Dependent Variable: ER						
b. Predictors: (Constant), JS, OT						

Source: Author’s Computation

Coefficient						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.617	.510		1.210	.228
	OT	.224	.061	.221	3.705	.000
	JS	.722	.062	.692	11.615	.000
a. Dependent Variable: ER						

Source: Author’s Computation

Table 8 above shows that the Adjusted R Square is 0.755, which is lower than R square = 0.758. This proves that the multiple regression model is appropriate for the data, and it will explain 75.8% of the variance in the data, which means that our independent variable, i.e., OT & JS, causes a 75.8% change in the dependent variable, i.e., ER. Since P- the P-value is .000, which is less than 0.01, we can say there is a significant relation between the independent variable and the dependent variable; thus, we accept both hypotheses, i.e., H1 & H2, i.e., online training and job satisfaction significantly affect employee retention. The coefficient results indicate that the beta value is (OT) 0.221 and (JS) 0.692, which means that the change in the independent variable, i.e., OT by one unit, will bring about the change in the dependent variable, i.e., ER by 0.221 units and change in independent variable JS by one unit will bring about the change in the dependent variable, i.e., ER by 0.692 units. Furthermore, the beta value is positive, which indicates a positive relationship between the independent variables OT & JS and the dependent variable ER.

Implications of the study:

Banks may benefit from the study's insights by creating more efficient HR policies and training initiatives to improve work satisfaction and staff retention. Resources for activities related to development and training that have been shown to have a good impact on retention may be deployed by banks with greater efficiency. The outcome of the study may help workers learn more about how to make use of the training possibilities that are available to them in order to enhance their career prospects and satisfaction with their jobs. Training providers may utilize the findings of the study to create more successful training programs by better personalizing them to the wants and needs of their staff members.

Limitations of the study:

Like other research work, this research too has some limitations, and these are as follows: the research investigation revolves around the Indian banking industry, and there may be constraints to the findings' generalization to other sectors of an economy or to regions with unique cultural and economic backgrounds. The quality and delivery of online training programs can differ greatly, which could have an effect on the consistency of outcomes obtained from various banks. The investigation could have neglected to take into account all external factors that might influence employee retention, such as market competition, legislative changes, financial circumstances, organizational culture, etc

CONCLUSION & FUTURE WORK

This study aims to gain a greater insight into how work satisfaction and online training are enhancing employee retention in the Indian banking industry. Although online training platforms enable adaptable, easily accessible, and personalized learning experiences that support employees' professional development and skill augmentation, they have become ever more significant in increasing job satisfaction. The evidence shows that employees are more likely to stay with their current employers when they feel that their employment is fulfilling and if they are provided with access to high-quality online training.

This highlights how important it is for banking organizations to spend money on both deploying contemporary training technology and establishing a positive work environment to increase staff involvement and retention. In the end, we conclude that online training and job satisfaction must be given top priority in the organization to retain employees for a long period of time. In the current research paper, we found that both online training and job satisfaction significantly affect employee retention.

The top authority in the organization must provide and hold training programs in the organization from time to time; online programs will enhance as well as develop their skill. This will not only lead to job satisfaction among them at the same time, but will also equip them to perform their task effectively and smoothly. Indian banks seeking to retain talent can, therefore, use an integrated strategy that involves blending strong online training programs with attempts to enhance workplace satisfaction. Banking firms can develop a more involved and committed staff by attending to both the immediate and ongoing skill development needs of their workers. Further, future researchers may examine various other factors, such as workplace environment, financial and non-financial benefits, etc., that affect employee retention.

Secondly, they may see the impact of these factors in other sectors, like the academic sector, employees of IT companies, business employees, etc. They may also increase the size of the respondents for more accurate and authentic results. Lastly, future researchers can do a comparative analysis of private and public banks to examine the effect of these variables in retaining talent, is more which type of bank.

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